

Excited state intramolecular proton transfer studies on the 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran in different solvents

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Abstract : Excited state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT) studies on the titled flavone has been studied in solvents having different physicochemical properties. Various spectral transitions have been assigned from the effect of solvents on its absorption spectra. Ratio of intensities of two emission bands (I_{N^*} and I_{T^*}) observed around 441.0 and 548.0 nm varies with solvent properties and are because of the multiparametric effect of solvents. Studies on the effect of viscosity of the medium have been studied in detail, where the total yield of emission is more and varies with viscosity. A linear relationship exist between I_{N^*}/I_{T^*} vs $\log \eta$, when viscosity of the medium is changed by adding ethylene glycol in propan-2-ol. Measurement of emission intensity ratio of the N^* and T^* bands, I_{N^*}/I_{T^*} can be useful as viscosity sensor.

Keywords : Excited state intramolecular proton transfer, viscosity sensor, dual emission, 3-hydroxyflavone.

Introduction

Proton transfer, in both ground and excited state is a fundamental process involved in chemical reactions as well as living systems^{1,2}. It is well established that the acidity or basicity of certain molecules are enhanced in the excited state as compared to the ground state. If both of these feature (one acidic and one basic) are in close proximity to each other in a molecule it is possible for a proton to "hop" from the acidic site to the basic one on excitation or otherwise. This kind of proton transfer from acidic to basic site of the molecule on excitation only is referred as Excited-State Intramolecular Proton Transfer (ESEPT) reaction³⁻⁹. Therefore, ESIPT has been defined as a reaction of tautomerization in which proton is trans-

ferred via intramolecular H-bond or H-bonding bridge formed by solvent molecules occurring in the excited states of molecules¹⁰. In most examples of molecules which undergo ESIPT, the acidic proton donor is a hydroxyl group and the basic acceptor is a nitrogen atom¹¹ or a carbonyl function¹². A common example of the latter type, which has been the subject of interest of a number of workers during the last twenty years, is 3-hydroxyflavone (3-HF) where a pyrrilium species is produced following ESIPT (Scheme 1).

Frolov and coworkers were the first who reported the dual fluorescence emission of 3-HF in alcoholic solvents¹³. The reversed interpretation of proton-transfer process was discovered by Sengupta and Kasha³, who assigned the

Scheme 1

dual fluorescence bands of 3-HF family. These flavones can provide information about the physicochemical properties of their microenvironment, both by the positions and the relative intensities of their two emission bands¹⁴. Measurements of the intensity ratio of the N* and T* bands, I_{N^*}/I_{T^*} , are very attractive possibilities to perform ratiometric detection, independent of flavones concentration and instrumental settings^{15,16}.

The absorption and fluorescence spectra of 3-HF have become a source of much valuable information on intermolecular interactions not only in neat solvents, but also in more complex, often microheterogeneous systems. Solvent dependence of ESIPT for the 3-HF's have been extensively studied specially during last twenty years¹⁷⁻²⁷. Demchenko and coworkers have demonstrated that the connection between solvent parameters and the absorption or emission spectra is essentially multiparametric and can not be reduced to simple "solvent polarity" scales.

In photochemistry the ESIPT reactions are known to be among the fastest elementary events: they can occur on the time scale of femtoseconds^{28,29}. These reactions are accompanied by a dramatic change in excited-state energies³⁰ and additional significant bathochromic shifts of emission wavelengths. The latter properties make their applications very promising in different fields, from laser dyes³¹ to molecular ion sensors^{32,33}. Due to these unique

features, numerous 3-hydroxychromones (3-HC) dyes have been used as new fluorescent probes for solvent polarity^{31,34,35}, ion binding³⁶, electric fields^{37,38}, reverse micelles^{39,40} etc.

We have recently reported the photochemistry of 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (3-HBP) but its clear mechanism could not be established⁴¹. For knowing the mechanistic features of photochemical reaction, it is desirable to look into the behavior and properties of excited state(s). This is because that the present study on the titled compound has been undertaken.

Results and discussion

Absorption bands in 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (3-HBP) :

Fig. 1 shows the UV/Visible absorption spectra of 3-HBP ($4.55 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) in different solvents whose structure is given below :

Chemical structure of 3-HBP

Fig. 1. UV/Vis absorption spectra of 3-HBP in different solvents. I to V are for cyclohexane, methanol, acetonitrile, acetonitrile : water, (v/v, 2 : 3) and methanol : water (v/v, 2 : 3) as solvents respectively.

For flavones and their hydroxyl substituted derivatives, absorption spectral region has been separated into two main set of absorption bands; commonly referred as band I (300–400 nm) and band II (240–280 nm). Likewise, here in 3-HBP there are two main bands, band I around 362 nm and band II around 257 nm along with a shoulder around 330.0 nm. As the data of the Table 1 shows that there is a red shift in band I of about 6 nm by going from non-polar (CH) and non-hydroxylic (acetonitrile)

pared with those in other solvents, the longest wavelength peak at 376 nm is missing in water and methanol and reduced to a shoulder in acetonitrile with a blue shift of 7 nm. This is because of the inert nature of cyclohexane solvent which differentiates the different sub bands. Therefore, this peak can be identified as the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions in the cinnamolic part of the molecule. While the peak at 358.0 nm in cyclohexane is red shifted by 7 nm by going to polar and hydroxylic solvents (methanol and water)

Table 1. Spectral data of 3-HBP in different solvents

Sl. no.	Solvents	η (cp) at 25 °C	ϵ^0 at 20 °C	Absorption bands λ_{\max} (nm)				
				Band I	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$	Band II	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$	Range of wavelength (nm) for shoulders
1.	CH	0.900	2.00	376.5,	0.199,	257.0	0.148	-
				358.0,	0.244,			-
				-	-			344.5–340.5
				330.5	0.141			-
2.	ACN	0.345	37.50	-	-	256.5	0.158	367.5–374.5
				358.0	0.220			-
				-	-			-
				-	-			333.0–328.0
3.	MeOH	0.547	32.63	-	-	257.0	0.130	-
				365.0	0.207			-
				-	-			-
				-	-			334.5–328.0
4.	H ₂ O : ACN (v/v, 3 : 2)	1.002	75.93	-	-	257.0	0.182	-
				364.0	0.280			-
				-	-			-
				-	-			340.0–332.0
5.	H ₂ O : MeOH (v/v, 3 : 2)	1.002	75.76	-	-	257.0	0.142	-
				366.0	0.173			-
				-	-			-
				-	-			341.0–334.0

CH - Cyclohexane, ACN - Acetonitrile, MeOH - Methanol.

ϵ - Molar Absorption Coefficient ($\text{dm}^{-3} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) and η - Viscosity.

ϵ^0 - Dielectric constant, which for the solvent mixture is calculated from the relation.

$C = \epsilon_{\text{organic solvent}} + W (\epsilon_{\text{water}} - \epsilon_{\text{organic solvent}})$.

W = Weight of water added per gram of the total amount of the solution.

trile) to polar (ACN : H₂O) and hydroxylic (methanol) media. This band is due to the cinnamolic part of the molecule. Band II which appears at 257 nm in all the solvents is due to the benzylic part of the molecule. Various peaks of the absorption spectra in different solvents when compared with the corresponding peaks in cyclohexane, some information about the $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions can also be obtained. In cyclohexane under the category of band I, there are three peaks at 376.5, 358.0 and 330.5 nm. When these bands are com-

should be due to, $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. Another peak at 330.5 nm and a shoulder around 342.0 nm in cyclohexane merge to one shoulder in other solvents with a little red shift should also be due to another $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in cinnamolic part. Band II at 257 nm, position of which remains constant in different solvents should be due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions in benzylic part of the molecule.

Emission bands in 3-HBP :

Fig. 2 shows the emission spectra of 3-HBP in differ-

Fig. 2. Fluorescence spectra of 3-HBP in different solvents. I to V are for cyclohexane, isopropyl alcohol, acetonitrile : water (v/v, 1 : 4), acetonitrile : ethylene glycol (v/v, 1 : 4) and methanol respectively. Exciting wavelength (nm) – 358.0 for CH, 359.0 for ACN, 367.0 for ACN/IPA, 364.0 for MeOH and 358.0 for MeOH/EG.

ent solvents. Two bands appear in the range 370–670 nm. Band around 441.0 nm is due to normal form (N*) and around 548.0 nm is due to tautomeric form (T*) of 3-HBP in their excited states. Position and relative intensity of N* and T* states vary with the polarity of the solvents as shown in Table 2. Overall intensity of emission is markedly more in cyclohexane as compared to all other solvents. Ratio of intensity differs in all the solvents.

These observations for 3-HBP are similar to that observed for other flavones^{24,42,43}. It has been shown by different groups that in 3-HF's, the ESIPT reaction is much faster than the emission⁴⁴. Two emission bands belonging to N* and T*^{45,46} is due to rapidly established dynamic equilibrium between these forms^{47,48}. In highly purified and dried hydrocarbon solvents, no emission from the normal form (N*) of 3-HF is observed even at low tem-

Table 2. Emission data of 3-HBP in different solvents

Sl. no.	Solvents	α	β	Exciting wavelengths (nm) for 3-HF	Emission wavelengths (nm)		Relative emission intensity (I) due to		Emission intensity ratio (I_{T^*}/I_{N^*})
					$\lambda_{\max} N^*$	$\lambda_{\max} T^*$	N*	T*	
					1.	CH	0	0	
2.	ACN	0.07	0.32	359.0	427.0	547.0	9.71	76.05	7.83
3.	MeOH	0.43	0.47	364.0	434.0	547.0	23.86	52.20	2.19
4.	H ₂ O : ACN (v/v, 4 : 1)	0.82	0.35	364.0	441.0	529.0	9.21	15.29	1.66
5.	IPA : ACN (v/v, 4 : 1)	0.33	0.56	367.0	432.0	549.0	9.56	65.61	6.86
6.	EG : MeOH (v/v, 4 : 1)	-	-	358.0	442.0	547.0	67.17	65.62	0.98

CH - Cyclohexane, ACN - Acetonitrile, MeOH - Methanol, EPA - Isopropyl alcohol and EG - Ethylene glycol.

N* and T* - Excited states of normal and of tautomer form.

α and β - Hydrogen bond donor/acceptor capacity⁵³.

$\lambda_{\max} N^*$ and $\lambda_{\max} T^*$ are for the position of the fluorescence maxima of N* and T* forms, respectively.

perature⁴⁹, implying rapid ESIPT. The rate of intramolecular proton transfer in 2-(2'-hydroxyphenyl)benzothiazole (HBT) has been measured to be 170 ± 20 fs⁵⁰, demonstrating the need for femtosecond time resolution to measure ESIPT process. By observing the effect of adding methanol to the cyclohexane, it has been suggested that small quantities of methanol actually increased k_{PT} whereas an excess of methanol inhibit ESIPT. The same conclusion was arrived at from studies of 3-HF on an Ar matrix at 10 K^{51,52}. As shown in Table 2, 3-HBP has nearly all emission by its tautomer in cyclohexane showing that forward rate for $N^* \rightarrow T^*$ is very high. In case of acetonitrile or its mixture reaction with IPA backward transfer reaction to N^* from T^* does contribute. However in methanol, ACN/H₂O mixtures or MeOH/EG mixture, rates both ESIPT and backward transfer are comparable. These solvents differ in their polarity, acidity/basicity and viscosity. Cyclohexane is of low polarity, non hydroxylic solvent and so its behavior is different from others. Although ACN, IPA, methanol and EG have comparable polarity but differ in hydrogen donor properties. Water has highest polarity. IPA and EG are both hydrogen donors than others. EG is different especially in viscosity. Results also shows that in the case of EG significantly different result is that the total yield of emis-

sion (~ 130) is much more (< 85) than in other solvents except cyclohexane.

Effect of viscosity of the medium on the ESIPT :

It seems that some systematic ratiometric response of the two bands in the solvent differing in viscosity may also be used as a viscosity sensor. Although this kind of study on the effect of other parameters of the solvents like polarity, hydrogen donor capability etc. have been explored. But, the effect of viscosity has not noticed. Therefore, emission spectral studies of 3-HBP in EG have been studied in detail by taking different proportions of EG in ACN, IPA and MeOH. Relative viscosity of these different solvent mixtures has been measured by Ostwald viscometer kept in air thermostat at 26 ± 0.5 °C. Results are given in Tables 3 to 5. With increasing portions of EG, viscosity increases by about 15 times in MeOH and ACN and by about 5 times in IPA mixture. Ratio of emission intensity by tautomeric form (I_{T^*}) and normal form (I_{N^*}) constantly decreases. It is nearly halved in case of methanol and decreases by a factor of 7 in case of ACN and IPA. This change in ratio is mainly due to increasing emission intensity by N^* form, while the emission intensity by T^* form nearly remains constant. An empirical attempt has been made to relate this change in

Table 3. Effect of increasing EG proportions in MeOH on the emission data of 3-HBP

Sl. no.	% of Relative EG in MeOH (v/v)	Emission viscosity, η (cp)	Relative emission wavelengths (nm)		Emission intensity (I) due to		Emission intensity ratio (I_{T^*}/I_{N^*})
			N*	T*	N*	T*	
1.	0	0.59	438.0	548.0	105.91	230.27 ^a	2.17
2.	10	0.64	438.0	548.0	119.33	214.07	1.79
3.	20	0.71	438.0	548.0	142.81	235.09	1.65
4.	30	0.82	438.0	548.0	139.38	206.81	1.48
5.	40	1.00	439.0	548.0	155.52	199.05	1.28
6.	50	1.31	439.0	548.0	172.40	202.42	1.17
7.	60	1.70	441.0	548.0	196.03	219.81	1.12
8.	70	2.30	441.0	548.0	222.24	241.14	1.08
9.	80	3.20	442.0	548.0	252.15	272.19	1.08
10.	90	4.30	442.0	548.0	283.21	315.90	1.12

MeOH - Methanol, EG - Ethylene glycol and N^* and T^* - Excited states of normal and of tautomer.

^aMeasurements are made at high sensitivity of the spectrofluorimeter.

[3-HBP] - 6.01×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³. Exciting wavelength - 364.0 nm.

Table 4. Effect of increasing EG proportions in ACN on the emission data of 3-HBP

Sl. no.	% of Relative EG in ACN (v/v)	Emission viscosity, η (cp)	Relative emission wavelengths, (nm)		Emission intensity (I) due to		Emission intensity ratio (I_{T^*}/I_{N^*})
			N*	T*	N*	T*	
1.	0	0.48	427.0	546.0	32.6	282.9 ^a	8.67
2.	5	0.50	427.0	546.0	34.27	294.96	8.61
3.	10	0.54	432.0	546.0	66.2	258.9	3.91
4.	30	0.77	437.0	545.0	94.3	250.0	2.97
5.	40	0.90	437.0	545.0	113.3	250.8	2.21
6.	50	1.16	437.0	545.0	148.3	250.0	1.68
7.	60	1.65	437.0	545.0	173.4	262.8	1.52
8.	70	2.45	437.0	545.0	191.2	259.1	1.36
9.	80	3.75	437.0	545.0	218.2	267.8	1.23
10.	90	5.86	437.0	545.0	244.4	273.2	1.12
11.	95	7.00	437.0	545.0	255.3	279.6	1.10

ACN - Acetonitrile, EG - Ethylene glycol.

N* and T* - Excited states of normal and of tautomer.

^aMeasurements are made at high sensitivity of the spectrofluorimeter.[3-HBP] - 6.08×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, Exciting wavelength - 359.0 nm.**Table 5.** Effect of increasing EG proportions in IPA on the emission data of 3-HBP

Sl. no.	% of Relative EG in IPA (v/v)	Emission viscosity, η (cp)	Relative emission wavelengths (nm)		Emission intensity (I) due to		Emission intensity ratio (I_{T^*}/I_{N^*})
			N*	T*	N*	T*	
1.	0	1.48	430.0	548.0	37.89	265.65 ^a	7.01
2.	10	1.68	435.0	549.0	76.13	262.08	3.44
3.	20	1.90	436.0	549.0	101.14	261.04	2.58
4.	30	2.40	437.0	549.0	129.72	268.16	2.07
5.	40	2.90	437.0	549.0	148.13	263.59	1.78
6.	50	3.50	437.0	549.0	175.56	273.78	1.56
7.	60	4.40	437.0	549.0	195.37	279.20	1.43
8.	70	5.25	437.0	549.0	212.74	272.08	1.28
9.	80	7.00	437.0	549.0	233.95	274.64	1.17
10.	90	8.5	437.0	549.0	254.60	282.27	1.10

IPA - Isopropyl alcohol, EG - Ethylene glycol.

N* and T* - Excited states of normal and of tautomer.

^aMeasurements are made at high sensitivity of the spectrofluorimeter.[3-HBP] - 5.08×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, Exciting wavelength - 367.0 nm.

intensity of emission with changing viscosity of the medium. A linear plot between I_{N^*}/I_{T^*} vs $\log \eta$ (Fig. 3) has been obtained only where EG is added in IPA as solvent while this plot is non-linear in case of ACN and MeOH. One can surmise that the effect of viscosity can not be extra plotted for different cases, since this is highly specific and complex in nature. However, it is suggested that

with careful calibration of the two emission band ratio can be used as a viscosity (η) sensor like that this effect has been used for sensing the polarity of the solvents.

It can be concluded that the ratio of intensities of emission from normal and tautomeric form of 3-HBP, varies with the solvent properties especially viscosity of the medium.

Fig. 3. A plot of I_{N^*}/I_{T^*} vs $\log \eta$ of relative viscosity of the medium.

Experimental

Synthesis of 6-chloro-3-hydroxy-2-(2'-thienyl)-4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran (3-HBP) was carried out through a multiple sequence of reactions as reported earlier⁴¹.

All the reagents were purchased from Loba Chemical Co. For absorption and fluorescence studies, the solvents used were of spectroscopic grade. Distilled and de-ionized water was used which was obtained by double distillation over KMnO_4 .

Absorption spectra were measured with Double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer of Shimadzu (Pharmaspec 1700, Japan). Fluorescence emission spectra were recorded on a spectrofluorimeter (Shimadzu RF-5301PC, Japan) which has a range from 100 to 1000 nm. Both the instruments were equipped with advanced software which is connected to PC. Range of concentrations of substrate used for different sets were so adjusted that slight variation of concentration does not affect either the wavelength or the intensity of the emission bands.

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